
Final PhD Thesis Report

SUSTAIN

Understanding policy processes for
the institutionalisation of the One
Health approach across Europe

Responsible OHEJP Partner: Ann
Lindberg

Contributing external partners: Olivier Rubin

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INTRODUCTION

The final thesis or thesis report will be included in Deliverable 6.18 and the deadline to submit this deliverable to the European Commission is 30th June 2023. The deliverable will be a **public report** by default. **Where the final thesis report or final thesis contains information that must remain confidential under an embargoed period until the publications or outputs have been generated**, then a redacted version suitable for the public must be submitted.

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CONFIDENTIALITY

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1. PhD Project team composition

PhD student: Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden

University at which the PhD is registered: Roskilde University, Denmark.

Lead PhD Supervisor: Olivier Rubin, Roskilde University, Denmark.

Second Supervisor: Ann Lindberg, National Veterinary Institute, Sweden.

2. Abstract¹

This dissertation reveals drivers and constraints of the implementation of the One Health approach by investigating international non-governmental organisations, European Union (EU) agencies and some EU countries, plus Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. Additionally, two country cases, Sweden and Italy, provide practical examples by demonstrating agenda setting as well as knowledge translation processes, and the work carried out in government agencies and networks.

The dissertation has different methodological approaches. 1) A bibliometric analysis highlights challenges of cross-sector collaboration among scientists through publishing patterns and co-citation networks. 2) Further, a literature review indicates challenges for the environment sector and governance of the One Health approach. 3) Expert interviews were conducted to analyse One Health-related coordination, collaboration, and communication activities via the Swedish and Italian cases. 4) A survey study investigated the role of governance, agenda setting, and policymaking for the One Health approach.

Through the analyses of the individual papers and their synthesis, the dissertation arrives at three overarching conclusions. First, there are institutional barriers for One Health implementation. Main barriers that the dissertation investigated are silo working, agendas, and government agency set-ups. Government agencies can be fragmented and, to approach this, governments must determine clear criteria when establishing ministries and government agencies. To implement cross-sector One Health activities, the analysis points towards establishing institutional One Health strategies and incorporating specific problem definitions when designing One Health projects to tackle coordination issues. Second, there are knowledge translation challenges among scientists and between scientists and policymakers. These challenges must be addressed by leaders, problem brokers, and policy entrepreneurs. Scientific knowledge must be translated across sectors and to policymakers to create heterophil networks, use the knowledge that exists within networks, and to provide opportunities for actors from environment, social, and political science sectors to contribute to the knowledge pool. Third, there is a lack of understanding of the One Health approach. Efforts must be made to comprehend the approach and what it means generally, for institutes and for specific projects. Continuous capacity building for scientists must be performed to strengthen the use and operationalisation of the One Health approach.

For the OHEJP, the PhD project reveals opportunities to support One Health-related policymaking through considering knowledge translation and societal challenges. It proposes ways to maintain

¹ The chapters Abstract; Introduction and Objectives; Materials and Methods; Scientific Results and Discussion; Conclusions and Future work and perspectives draw on or are copied from the PhD dissertation: Humboldt-Dachroeden, S. (2023). Understanding policy processes for the institutionalisation of the One Health approach across Europe [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Roskilde University.

cooperative structures (e.g., with policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers, honing leadership skills and strengthening heterophil networks). It presents drivers and constraints of One Health institutionalisation. The PhD project's impact for the OHEJP stakeholders include practical examples about possible applications of social and environmental scientists and a call to engage eastern European countries in One Health-related activities. Lastly, the impact for national ministries and institutes are lessons that can be learnt from the cases to strengthen future One Health approaches and activities. The studies highlight the need to establish scope, strategies, and harmonise data for international surveillance activities to prevent duplication and strengthen efficacy.

3. Introduction and Objectives

Disease outbreaks, epidemics, and pandemics are a historically recurring theme affecting humans and animals around the world. The likelihood of their occurrence is increasing due to climatic and anthropogenic changes, and they are likely to be zoonotic diseases. Approximately 60% of all infectious diseases are estimated to be zoonoses. Zoonoses are diseases or infections that are able to spread between animals and humans (Jones et al., 2008). Countries prepare for zoonoses, other infectious diseases, and health threats differently. While there are similarities in disease prevention and management, there is no coherent approach, not least due to the different health threats facing the countries, depending on a myriad of factors, including climate, geography, culture, and many more (Mayer, 2000). Usually, there are formalised procedures in place to tackle disease outbreaks, often involving government agencies, such as public health and veterinary institutes, as well as municipalities and local-level health services. If animals or plants in the food and feed industry are affected, the industrial and agricultural sectors also become involved (Mazet et al., 2014). To prevent outbreaks, countries have disease surveillance systems in place, often with international reporting obligations, such as to the European Union (EU) or the World Health Organization (WHO) (Villarreal, 2022).

Health threats such as zoonoses are usually events affecting more than one sector or community. Hence, there are usually more sectors involved in addressing them. As described above, the public health and veterinary institutes are usually involved, but environment and food institutes can also contribute. The engagement of those sectors implies the interconnectedness of humans, animals, and the environment in preventing and responding to disease outbreaks. This is in line with the One Health approach, which allows for the inclusion of human health considerations, as well as considerations regarding the health of animals and the environment. One Health is defined as

an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the health of people, animals and ecosystems. It recognizes the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and inter-dependent. (OHHLEP et al., 2022, p. 2)

However, the institutional structures and political processes for implementing the One Health approach are unclear. Therefore, this dissertation examines institutional abilities and boundaries to coordinate One Health issues and the political processes in place to address them.

“One Health is not an arrival point, it is the starting point.”² This statement was made by an expert

² From interview study 2021. Respondent's workplace: Public health institute, Italy.

from the Italian public health institute, and it is an important notion to recognise for institutes as well as politics that use One Health as a rhetorical and institutional approach to addressing health threats. The One Health approach provides tools, techniques, and networks to prevent and prepare for disease outbreaks, using coordinated surveillance, from local to global levels. The health threats that the approach usually encompasses are zoonotic and infectious diseases, as well as antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (Zinsstag et al., 2020). AMR is a global problem and it describes the ability of microbes to resist conventional treatments (e.g., antibiotics) (Baekkeskov et al., 2020). One Health also encompasses health threats relating to environmental issues such as pollution, biodiversity loss and climate change, albeit often to a lesser extent (dos S. Ribeiro et al., 2019).

Implementing and institutionalising the One Health approach can assume different shapes and forms. In this context, institutionalisation means the establishment of structures, processes, and conditions that make the One Health approach tangible and a standard within institutes. On an international level, efforts are undertaken by non-governmental organisations (NGOs) or within the EU, by the European Commission and EU agencies. On a national level, there can be surveillance activities implemented by governments. Industries, schools, and universities can also contribute to realising the One Health approach within countries. On an institutional level, efforts include cross-sector collaboration via research projects or disease outbreak activities. Figure 1 presents examples of One Health approaches on international, national, and institutional levels.

INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

- Action plans (e.g., the European One Health Action Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance)
- International networks (e.g., the Quadripartite consisting of the FAO, WOA, WHO, and UNEP*)
- International research activities (e.g., EU's Horizon 2020 projects)

NATIONAL LEVEL

- Surveillance activities of zoonotic diseases and AMR
- Data sharing platforms
- Inspections within the food and feed industry
- Campaigns
- School or university curricula

INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL

- Joint research projects
- Coordinated outbreak activities
- Interdisciplinary meetings, conferences, and networks

Figure 1: Implementing the One Health approach on international, national, and institutional levels³

* FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, WOA: World Organisation for Animal Health, UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

However, implementing the One Health approach raises institutional challenges, which can pertain to connecting different sectors, such as public health, veterinary, environment and food services, which are often categorised under different ministries and, hence, receive different mandates. Mandates for

³ International level: (European Commission, 2017; One Health EJP, 2021; WHO, 2022b); National level: (Haxton et al., 2015; Kelly et al., 2020; Landford & Nunn, 2012; Mazet et al., 2014; Newitt et al., 2018); Institutional level: (Bordier et al., 2021).

the respective government institutions translate into agendas reflecting specific priorities and interests, which may not align. For example, the health and environmental programmes of governments and institutions are often seen as separate entities that do not influence one another (Manlove et al., 2016). This complicates the possibility of working in an interdisciplinary manner and across sectors towards a combined goal (Craddock & Hinchliffe, 2015; Manlove et al., 2016). Furthermore, institutes and agencies dealing with similar issues at the human–animal–environment interface have different communication infrastructures, priorities, and ambitions to implement the One Health approach. The One Health approach also struggles with data-sharing challenges across sectors, as health- and industry-related information is often sensitive. Further, municipalities and governments often struggle to provide institutions with funding and logistics for interdisciplinary activities (dos S. Ribeiro et al., 2019; Lee & Brumme, 2013). Attracting political attention to One Health issues can be cumbersome, as political decision- and policymakers must consider information from multiple disciplines and sectors. Collaboration across disciplines and sectors also depends on personal relations, willingness, and mutual understandings (Rüegg et al., 2018).

The dissertation explores some of the institutional aspects that can challenge the implementation of the One Health approach with the aim to enhance the understanding of the challenges and how to address them. Moreover, it provides insight into opportunities that institutions and politics can use to strengthen the approach. This dissertation investigates international NGOs, EU agencies, some EU countries, plus Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. The two country cases, Sweden and Italy, are also included. The aspects explored in this research are experienced and expressed by experts (e.g., scientists, policymakers) in the many fields of One Health. Building on interviews in Swedish and Italian public health, veterinary, food, and environment institutes, and on a survey of key health experts across Europe, the research question for the PhD project is:

What are the key institutional drivers and constraints on the effective implementation of the One Health approach?

The research question is supported by analytical steps that represent the methodological approach and establish the process of the project. A first step was a literature review, which was accompanied by a bibliometric analysis that informed subsequent studies. The second analytical step included qualitative research interviews with experts from Sweden and Italy in the public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors. This provided input for the two cases, Sweden and Italy, in the form of qualitative insights into institutional and political structures impacting the implementation of the One Health approach. The final analytical step was a survey to collect data regarding the governance of the One Health approach in national government and research institutions, ministries, and international organisations (EU agencies and NGOs). This provided insight into One Health policymaking and governance; One Health network interactions and relationships; and specific One Health topics, such as AMR and the engagement of the environment sector. Accumulated, these steps provide different angles and perspectives, which, when synthesised, contribute to answering the research question.

3.1. Relevance

The literature examining One Health describes some of the main challenges facing the approach in terms of the interdisciplinary and cross-sector implementation of activities (dos S. Ribeiro et al., 2019). The terms ‘sectors’ and ‘disciplines’ are frequently used in the One Health field. The definition of One Health, referred to above, continues and emphasises the importance of engaging different sectors,

disciplines, actors, and communities to approach interdisciplinary health threats, including broader notions of sustainable development (see full definition in Figure 2) (OHHLEP et al., 2022). Actors engaged in the One Health approach can be found in different sectors, meaning areas of activity that are separated from one another due to their specific topics (e.g., agricultural sector, scientific sector, political sector, industrial sector, public health sector, environment sector, veterinary sector) (Bordier et al., 2021). Such actors can be scientists, bureaucrats, policy actors, health professionals, farmers, etc. (Mazet et al., 2014). Within the sectors are different disciplines, of which the dissertation refers to scientific disciplines. Within public health research, for example, there are epidemiology or health policy disciplines; veterinary research includes food safety and animal welfare; and within environmental research are ecology and biology. Of course, there are also intersections across sectors with the same disciplines but approached with different perspectives (e.g., microbiology and toxicology can be performed within the public health, veterinary, and environmental disciplines).

The many sectors, disciplines, and actors involved highlight the complexity of the One Health approach. The observed national or institutional challenges can relate to funding, capacity, silo thinking, and conveying between science and politics (dos S. Ribeiro et al., 2019). Such challenges can inhibit interdisciplinary and cross-sector collaboration and communication, which can lead to isolated and redundant efforts (Connolly, 2017; Manlove et al., 2016; Mateus et al., 2022). Further, the scientific literature on One Health implementation often pertains to a specific topic, such as a zoonotic disease, or has a one- or two-sided perspective often concentrating only on the medical and veterinary sectors. Hence, scholars have pointed out the need to reshape institutions and processes with the help of leadership to strengthen knowledge sharing and facilitate the coordination of interdisciplinary and cross-sector One Health activities (Connolly, 2017; Stephen & Stemshorn, 2016).

There are international activities aimed at tackling One Health issues, including data gathering, surveillance, and monitoring activities (e.g., by the EU or WHO: ECDC et al., 2017; WHO et al., 2016), and approaches that facilitate guidance and support within countries (FAO et al., 2019). Nonetheless, difficulties are experienced when coordinating and implementing collaborations, guidance, plans, and surveillance activities (dos S. Ribeiro et al., 2019; Munkholm et al., 2021). For instance, data security and sharing regulations often challenge data sharing across sectors and countries. If data sharing is feasible, another issue can be the lack of harmonised data or analytical approaches, which can impede comparisons or slow down research (Asokan & Asokan, 2015; Lebov et al., 2017).

The literature points towards existing legal frameworks and opportunities; for example, the International Health Regulations, an international legal treaty, that can be a useful tool to address some One Health-related topics, specifically in relation to infectious diseases. Specifying the One Health approach within the regulations could establish a more comprehensive One Health strategy that facilitates the harmonisation of standards and surveillance activities (Gostin & Katz, 2016). However, revising the International Health Regulations may prove difficult due to a lack of political will (Rogers Van Katwyk et al., 2020). Local, national, and regional (e.g., the EU) approaches open other legal and regulatory possibilities for implementing the One Health approach. Stewardship programmes have been established, for example for AMR (Aryee & Price, 2015; Keith et al., 2016; Rüegg et al., 2017), One Health action plans (European Commission, 2017), as well as national strategies (Danish Ministry of Health & Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, 2017; German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2021), and other activities to coordinate surveillance or other One Health-related activities (EFSA & ECDC, 2019; Haxton et al., 2015; Swedish University of

Agricultural Sciences, 2022). Nevertheless, the disadvantages include how some of these regulations are non-binding, which can entail inactivity or poor implementation, and scientists also pointed out a lack of education and knowledge for performing some of the activities (dos S. Ribeiro et al., 2019; Garcia & Gostin, 2012).

The literature indicates a missing element that can facilitate the implementation of One Health activities, projects and policies: the social and political science sectors (Craddock & Hinchliffe, 2015; Lapinski et al., 2015; Mazet et al., 2014; Woldehanna & Zimicki, 2015). The social and political sciences offer tools that allow for analyses that include cultural, societal, anthropological, economic, political, and even philosophical perspectives. This can aid our understanding of what One Health means for different projects and in different circumstances. It can determine the importance of specific contexts, organisational structures, and governance processes. Insights into these aspects can contribute to the understanding of local and global realities; institutions in terms of organisation and networks; and political aspects such as science and policy mediation, agenda-setting, policymaking, and implementation (Michalon, 2020; Queenan et al., 2016). Scholars have also pointed out the absence and limited consideration of the legal and ethical sectors (Coghlan et al., 2021; Degeling et al., 2015; Phelan & Gostin, 2017). This dissertation will particularly identify some of the entry points for social, political, and economic scientists and their specific contributions, which are needed to enhance One Health activities.

As described above, scholars have found many challenges for implementing the One Health approach. However, these challenges often represent very broad issues and lack in-depth investigations of the fundamental issues causing or contributing to them. The opportunities and facilitating factors for implementing the One Health approach in the European context have remained under-explored. This dissertation seeks to address these gaps by advancing scholarly understanding of more specific issues for implementing One Health activities, especially in relation to institutional constraints, governance, leadership, coordination, and knowledge translation. Further, the dissertation addresses the lack of theory for the One Health approach by contributing to the discussion of philosophical and theoretical notions for it. By addressing these gaps in the literature and theory, the aim is to enhance the general understanding of One Health together with the underlying structures necessary to implement the approach.

3.2. Background

The 'One Health' term has been around for a few years, but notions connecting the health of humans, animals, and even the environment can be traced back to the BCE times. The One Health approach distinguishes between humans and animals. Although humans belong to the animal kingdom, this distinction is regularly used, and animals are sometimes described as 'non-human animals'. Discussions about the distinction have been going on for thousands of years (see, e.g., Aristotle et al., 1908), and they explore many philosophical questions regarding consciousness, rationality, and other aspects. For the sake of simplicity, this dissertation refers to animals and humans, albeit with an awareness that humans are technically animals.

The main topics of the One Health approach are zoonotic diseases and AMR, but the environment also plays a pivotal role in facilitating or compromising the health of ecosystems, humans, and animals. A brief overview is provided to highlight the intertwined relationships between humans, animals, and the environment in view of the following One Health topics:

Zoonotic diseases are infectious diseases that can transmit back and forth between animals and humans. Such diseases can emerge locally but can also spread and affect neighbouring and even global communities. Animal-to-human disease transmission can occur in any environment where humans and animals meet, directly or indirectly; for instance, during livestock farming, through contact with wild animals, at markets, and through companion animals. But there are more defined pathways through which zoonotic pathogens (bacteria, viruses, parasites) can spread: They can be vector-borne (via insects), foodborne, waterborne, airborne, and many others (Plowright et al., 2017). Zoonotic diseases are not a new phenomenon. Outbreaks have occurred repeatedly in history, with epidemics and pandemics such as the bubonic plague (1347–1352, still sporadically occurring), the Spanish Flu (1918–1920), Ebola (first discovered in 1976), HIV-1 (first reported case in 1981), and SARS (2002–2004) – just to name a few (Jedwab et al., 2020; Jones et al., 2008). However, how we address outbreaks through prevention, detection, surveillance, and mitigation efforts has changed. We are living in a world that is more connected or globalised via trade, tourism and business (Amuasi et al., 2020). This provides opportunities for pathogens, as the popular phrase ‘diseases know no borders’ indicates. A disease can spread from one side of the world to the other in a matter of hours. The spread of COVID-19 was a recent such incident; officially first detected in December 2019 in the Chinese city of Wuhan and facilitated by globalisation, the pathogen quickly travelled around the globe (WHO, 2020). The environment has been a crucial pathway for the spread and transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 virus that causes COVID-19, as it can spread through the air and contaminated surfaces. It was also detected in sewage, including in Italy and the Netherlands (La Rosa et al., 2021; SanJuan-Reyes et al., 2021). The virus transmits between humans but also across species; for example, from humans to pets, and zoo animals (dogs, (big) cats, primates), between humans and livestock (mink), and the likely origin of the virus from wild animals (Fenollar et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2020; Murphy & Ly, 2021).

AMR is another regularly mentioned One Health issue. Simply put, AMR occurs when microbes such as bacteria, fungi, viruses or parasites mutate so that conventional treatments fail (e.g., antibiotics for bacterial infections). The microbes mutate naturally, but there is extra pressure to mutate on them when medicines (like antibiotics) are extensively (mis-)used. When microbes mutate, they can become resistant to the medicines used for treatment. There are few alternative treatments and few possibilities for new drug development, which reduces the options for medications and therapy (Holmes et al., 2016). Hence, AMR threatens the ability to treat infections in humans, animals, and plants around the world and raises global concerns. Plants in horticulture, for example, are affected through the use of pesticides, which can contain antibiotics (Malagón-Rojas et al., 2020). These pesticides can additionally contribute to the spread of AMR in the environment (via soil, water, other plants) (Liao et al., 2021). Further, intensive livestock farming increases the risk of AMR as well as of zoonotic disease outbreaks. In intensive livestock farming practices, thousands of animals can be in close proximity, risking animal welfare and facilitating disease transmission. This can in turn increase the use of antimicrobials, contributing to the spread of resistant microbes between the animals, to humans and in the environment (Coghlan et al., 2021; Klous et al., 2016). There is an occupational hazard of AMR for all involved in agriculture, livestock farming, and meat production; not least for farmers, their families, and slaughterhouse workers, but also the communities near farms (Karesh et al., 2012). Further, antimicrobials are sometimes (unintentionally) misused by human and animal doctors, farmers, and consumers due to a lack of knowledge concerning AMR, prescribing or dosage errors. Misuse, wrong usage and the inadequate disposal of antimicrobials also contribute to the spread of AMR (Hinchliffe et al., 2018; Kahn, 2017).

In addition to zoonotic diseases and AMR, the One Health approach can provide insight into **environmental issues** that are closely linked to human and animal health (Essack, 2018). The environment can impact the spread of pathogens through a myriad of potential pathways, including air, water (e.g., rivers, wastewater), soil and surfaces (Plowright et al., 2017). Environmental contamination via, for example, toxic metals, toxic compounds (e.g., mycotoxins produced by fungi), pesticides, and microplastic can exacerbate pollution that is harmful for the ecosystem, human, and animal health (Davies et al., 2021; Frazzoli et al., 2017; Levin et al., 2020; Prata et al., 2021). The climate is an important indicator of environmental changes. Climatic changes like varying temperatures, extreme weather conditions (e.g., droughts, torrential rainfall) affect the health of the environment, animals, and humans alike (Humboldt-Dachroeden & Mantovani, 2021). The consequences of climate change are severe for biodiversity, and it affects the habitats of animals and humans who must adapt or migrate to areas with more favourable conditions (McMahon et al., 2018; McMichael et al., 2012). For example, ticks are moving into warmer regions where they have not previously been detected, which can contribute to the spread of tick-borne diseases (Black & Butler, 2014). Another example is the parasite *plasmodium*, which causes malaria. Garamszegi (2010) has revealed how the parasite benefits from rising temperatures, as they are optimal for reproduction. Hence, wild birds and potentially humans are at an increasing risk of malaria infection due to climate change. Other consequences that are already being experienced include extreme weather conditions, the aftermath of which are often perfect breeding grounds for diseases. Anthropogenic activities can influence the health of the environment. One such activity is deforestation, which once again closes the circle to human and animal health by leading to a loss of biodiversity and to closer animal–human proximity. This destabilises the ecosystem and promotes the spread of zoonotic and infectious diseases (Redford et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2016).

The complex, interconnected, and by no means complete list of aspects of disease-transmission pathways and their impacts indicate the value of a multifaceted approach like One Health. This is highlighted by scientists who have voiced repeated concerns and warnings of AMR, emerging or re-emerging disease outbreaks that can turn into pandemics (e.g., Aryee & Price, 2015; Epstein, 2001; Hsieh et al., 2006; Jones et al., 2008; Majumder et al., 2020; Webster, 1997). Such issues present themselves as natural science and medical challenges, but they also affect societies, economies, and politics (Degeling et al., 2015; Michalon, 2020).

3.2.1. Brief history of the One Health approach

A fundamental consideration of the One Health approach is to shed light on the definition and meaning of One Health, which implies an understanding of the definition(s) of health. This paragraph will not go into detail in this very broad field, merely touching on the surface to give an understanding of the difficulties of defining health for One Health. The WHO defines health as ‘a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity’ (WHO, 2006). However, this definition is tailored to human health, to the individual being, and neglects all non-human animals, as well as the environment (Lerner & Berg, 2015). Establishing broader considerations for health, the Determinants of Health Model provides explanations for environmental influences on our health (see section 1.2.2) (Barton & Grant, 2006). This is obviously human-centred, but it highlights socio-political considerations as well as the effect that the environment can have on humans and vice versa.

There are few concrete definitions for animal health, and those that exist have different perspectives, such as health connected to the absence/presence of disease, to biological function/malfunction, to homeostasis (which is the balance of physiological processes), to physical and psychological well-being, and to reproduction (Gunnarsson, 2006). There are few definitions emphasising moral considerations for animals (Coghlan et al., 2021). The definitions are usually disconnected from humans and sometimes even pets, as they are ‘non-producing’ animals (Gunnarsson, 2006).

The health of the environment is also a complex matter. Importantly, this is not to be confused with the term ‘environmental health’, which refers to a discipline within public health that studies, assesses, and monitors the impact of the environment on human health (European Environment Agency, 2023). The health of the environment might be more closely related to the definition of ecosystem health, which can be understood in a metaphorical or literal manner (Lerner, 2019). The more often used metaphorical definition describes the health of the ecosystem being based on ‘goods and services they provide to humans’ (Palmer & Febria, 2012, p. 1393). This alone, however, does not give justice to the ecosystem itself and centres again on humans. Instead, the definition, especially when used for the One Health approach, should include the structure of ecosystems that can be evaluated through different indicators, which can ‘reflect the existing status or condition of an ecosystem’ (Palmer & Febria, 2012, p. 1393).

While this dissertation is not set out to produce a holistic definition of health, particularly health at the human–animal–environment interface, it is important to understand that this requires consideration and attention. It is established that health is not merely the absence of diseases, but it remains difficult to capture all the aspects, dimensions, and layers of health (Lerner, 2019). This is crucial to address for the One Health approach, as it is the basis for each activity and project. Further, it is relevant to mention the different perspectives a One Health activity can have: the individual or the population approach. Human medicine traditionally takes an individual approach, concentrating on the individual in terms of health protection and promotion, and public health focuses on populations (Arah, 2009). Veterinary health uses both population and individual approaches, concentrating on the health outcomes of individual animals, a group of humans or animals, or both (Gibbs & Gibbs, 2013). The environment takes the whole system into account; hence, it is often referred to as an ecosystem approach (Lerner & Berg, 2015). These differentiations and distinctions are important to consider, as they are the building blocks for One Health projects and activities.

As mentioned above (section 1.2), the thought of health being connected across species and environments is no novel concept. The Greek physician Hippocrates (460–367 BCE) integrated comparative medicine practices by studying humans and animals in their anatomy and pathology of diseases (Day, 2011). He emphasised the importance of a clean environment, including the quality of clean water, for ‘good health’ (Jouanna, 2012). The understanding of the environment, physiology and medicine have advanced greatly since then, not least due to new technologies and notions (e.g., discovery of the DNA (1951 by Rosalind Franklin), development of electron microscopy (1931 by Ernst Ruska and Max Knoll), invention of vaccines (already used in the 16th century and likely before that in China or India, established and popularised by Edward Jenner in 1796), and discovery of antibiotics (already used by ancient Sudanese people and Egyptians from 350 CE, discovered by Alexander Flemming in 1928) (Aminov, 2010; Cramer, 2020; Lombard et al., 2007; Savage et al., 2018)). Further, two new terms that would prove crucial for the One Health approach were coined. The first was ‘zoonosis’, indicating a link between human and animal diseases, which the German physician and

pathologist Rudolf Virchow (1827–1902) introduced. He also emphasised the importance of environmental determinants for health outcomes (Capua & Cattoli, 2018). The second term was coined in 1964 by Calvin Schwabe. He introduced the concept of ‘One Medicine’ to emphasise the similarities between human and veterinary medicine and to highlight how collaboration can complement the development of each other’s sector (Zinsstag et al., 2011). The One Medicine concept was further developed at the 2004 Wildlife Conservation Society symposium ‘One World, One Medicine’, which highlighted the need for multidisciplinary work to promote surveillance, preparedness, prevention, and emergency systems, and to influence policymaking at the human–animal–ecosystem interface (FAO et al., 2008). In 2010, the FAO, WOA, and WHO committed to a Tripartite engagement, aiming to achieve ‘One Health goals’, such as reducing the emergence and spread of diseases through cross-sector collaboration and coordination (FAO et al., 2010). This was followed by a strategic document, which renewed the commitment of the organisations and broadened the work on One Health issues (FAO et al., 2017). In 2019, the Tripartite organisations published a guide to aid member states in implementing and addressing zoonotic diseases and AMR through cross-sector collaboration together with the management and coordination of the One Health approach (FAO et al., 2019). The Tripartite engaged the UNEP to include the environment perspective more explicitly in their efforts, which led to the Tripartite evolving to the Quadripartite. In 2022, this formation was made official in a joint press report (WHO, 2022b). In 2020, the Tripartite initiated the creation of the One Health High-Level Expert Panel. The aim of the 26 international experts is to establish a ‘long-term strategic approach to reducing the risk of zoonotic pandemics’ and to give policy advice to the Quadripartite (WHO, 2022a). Early in the engagement, the One Health High-Level Expert Panel developed their explanation for what One Health is and arrived at the definition and illustration in Figure 2. The definition has three parts, the first being a general explanation of One Health, the second points to who is involved and why, and the third describes key concepts, topics, and actors. This definition is used in the dissertation, as it provides a good overview of the One Health approach.

- ➔ One Health is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the health of people, animals and ecosystems.
- ➔ It recognizes the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and inter-dependent.
- ➔ The approach mobilizes multiple sectors, disciplines and communities at varying levels of society to work together to foster well-being and tackle threats to health and ecosystems, while addressing the collective need for clean water, energy and air, safe and nutritious food, taking action on climate change, and contributing to sustainable development.

Figure 2: Definition and illustration of the One Health approach (OHHLEP et al., 2022)

Within the EU, the notion of considering health more comprehensively has already been incorporated to some extent since the Brundtland Report, which was a key initiator for considering and integrating sustainable development within policies (European Commission, 2001). The report was published in 1987, and sustainable development plays a key role in promoting resource efficiency, sustainable cities as well as economies and social cohesion (Brundtland, 1987). As sustainable development is mentioned in the latest definition of One Health by the One Health High-Level Expert Panel, and the Brundtland Report mentions the main One Health topics (e.g., the animal ecosystem, human health, environment, and communicable diseases), there are clear parallels between the approaches. Further, the United Nations Millennium Development Goals and the ensuing Sustainable Development Goals shaped EU decision- and policymaking in many policy areas related to the health of humans, animals, and the environment (Grieg-Gran, 2003; Koman et al., 2020). One Health has arrived as a recognised and stand-alone approach in the EU. The EU has expressed its commitment especially in relation with AMR, and the European One Health Action Plan against AMR was adopted in 2017. Here, the EU pledges to enhance surveillance activities with an inclusive plan across human, animal, and environmental sectors (European Commission, 2017). The European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) has integrated One Health notions by providing input into how to strengthen One Health preparedness strategies (ECDC, 2018). Additionally, the EU zoonoses report has included an explicit One Health perspective since 2018 (EFSA & ECDC, 2019). With funding for interdisciplinary research projects, the EU further aims to increase research and development in One Health or specific One Health topics (e.g., zoonotic diseases like zika virus, AMR, and food systems) (European Commission, 2020).

All in all, One Health appears to represent a well-intentioned approach to tackling interconnected health issues in a globalised world (Garcia & Gostin, 2012); however, the approach has also been criticised. One of the main points of criticism is that the Western-centred idea of health is imposed in (non-Western) contexts in which the relations between humans and animals/the environment are different due to distinct values, farming practices, and economic conditions (Baquero et al., 2021). Power relations are at play, and the effects of colonialism and post-colonialism must be taken into account (Davis & Sharp, 2020). The One Health approach has a global perspective, often focusing on countries, regions, or areas where there are many (emerging) zoonotic diseases. These are often lower-income countries, affected by climate change and (post-)colonialism (Garcia & Gostin, 2012). Although the PhD project focuses on Europe, there is value in considering collisions of Western notions and post-colonialism. Sweden, for example, has an indigenous population: the Sami. Indigenous peoples typically have strong connections with animals and the environment (Garnier et al., 2020). Government rules and regulations sometimes go against the animal- and environment-related practices of indigenous peoples (Bjärstig et al., 2020). This clash emphasises the need for sensitive and careful considerations. There is no one-size-fits-all One Health approach. Contexts, circumstances, and histories must be considered (Garnier et al., 2020). Knowledge from indigenous people is not only important to comprehend how they do things, but they are a valuable contribution to enhancing the knowledgebase of the humans–animals–environment interconnection (Baquero et al., 2021; Garnier et al., 2020).

3.2.2. Other complementary approaches

Other initiatives and notions have similar objectives to the One Health approach. One of these is referred to as **Planetary Health**, which is a field that takes into account the broader socio-economic and political perspectives in relation to the anthropogenic impact of humans on the planet. Hence, the focus is on human health and human systems (political, economic, social, cultural, equity, and equality) (Alonso Aguirre et al., 2019). Animal health and welfare are described, but especially in relation to food production and disease transmission. The environment is considered, for example regarding sustainability, but mainly in relation to human health outcomes (Lerner & Berg, 2017).

Conversely, **EcoHealth** involves a systems-thinking approach focused on ecosystems, especially on healthy ecosystems that allow for healthy humans and animals. The purpose is to comprehend socio-economic, equity, and ecological (including biodiversity) aspects that affect health. Apart from the natural sciences, the approach employs social sciences as well as anthropology, and it makes an effort to include local and indigenous knowledge (Lerner & Berg, 2017). However, this approach has struggled with ‘operation criteria in relation to their design, implementation and evaluation’ (Alonso Aguirre et al., 2019, p. 7).

Planetary Health, EcoHealth, and One Health do share some core notions, especially regarding human health. They differ regarding their main focuses, methodological approaches, and scope (Lerner & Berg, 2017). The approaches all struggle with disciplinary silos as well as the lack of coherent, cross-sector data (Hitziger et al., 2021; Leung et al., 2012). For the EcoHealth and One Health approaches, it has been suggested to integrate a systems thinking approach to comprehend the interconnectedness across sectors and actors, to manage knowledge from multiple sources, and to operationalise the approaches (Hitziger et al., 2018; Zinsstag, 2012). This remains a challenge for the approaches, however, as there is a lack of competencies and institutional measures to employ systems thinking. Another aspect that convolutes One Health as well as Planetary Health and EcoHealth is that the

approaches involve the natural sciences while affecting many other sectors, such as ‘politics (health, agriculture, aquaculture, land management, urbanism, and biological conservation), law, and ethics’ (Destoumieux-Garzón et al., 2018, p. 10). The involvement of those disciplines is still not very widespread, albeit crucial as a fundamental element in the planning and implementing of the approaches (Degeling et al., 2015; Lapinski et al., 2015).

Barton and Grant (2006) presented their further-developed **Determinants of Health Model**. Based on the layered model of Whitehead and Dahlgren (1991), it includes detailed health determinants such as lifestyle factors, social networks, equity, socio-economic, cultural, political, as well as environmental conditions. In the model, the individual human is inside an ecosystem within its own habitat surrounded by forces and determinants that can affect its well-being (Barton & Grant, 2006; Whitehead & Dahlgren, 1991). These determinants are influenced and affected by different aspects, including biodiversity, climate change, and communities, as well as economic, political, and cultural systems (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Determinants of Health Model further developed by Barton and Grant (Barton & Grant, 2006)

This model can be used to complement the One Health approach by considering the contexts in which humans live. It implies connections to the environment as well as animals by referring to ‘biodiversity’ and ‘natural environments’, which can be used to enhance the understanding of human–animal–environment interactions. Further, socio-political considerations can illuminate power relations as well as local and national realities, they can account for effects of globalisation and provide an understanding of the vulnerability of different populations (Craddock & Hinchliffe, 2015). The

Quadrupartite (at that time a Tripartite) also highlights the importance of considering the determinants of health as a key model in understanding the conditions and factors of daily life. Considering gender, involving social scientists, engaging communities, minorities, and indigenous populations is encouraged to be included as a practice to strengthen the development of One Health activities and policies (FAO et al., 2019).

In line with these considerations, **The Lancet One Health Commission** has recognised the interrelated nature of One Health that is influenced by the prevailing political, cultural, social, and economic contexts (see outer ring in Figure 4). Similar to the Determinants of Health Model, it integrates different layers of potential health impacts (Amuasi et al., 2020). While Barton and Grant (2006) outline environmental influences in detail, connecting them with climate change and biodiversity, *The Lancet One Health Commission* emphasised our shared environment with companion animals, wildlife, and animals in agriculture (see Figure 4). Considering both models will be beneficial when establishing interdisciplinary collaboration, communication, and coordination from local to global levels. It can inform the implementation of activities and policies that are based on sound socio-economic, political, as well as ethical considerations, and it can protect and promote the health of humans, animals, and environments.

Figure 4: One Health approach integrating broader socio-political perspectives (Amuasi et al., 2020)

3.3. Objectives

The objective of the PhD project was to investigate the drivers and constraints of One Health institutionalisation in Europe. The aim was to enhance the understanding of the challenges in relation to One Health institutionalisation and how to address them. The dissertation is located within the social sciences and is article-based, meaning that per Roskilde University's regulations at least three articles have to be produced. Of the three articles, at least two must be single-authored (without co-authors). I produced six papers in total, five scientific articles of which two are co-authored and three single-authored, and one co-authored chapter of an edited book (see list of papers under chapter 7, output).

3.3.1. Expected outcomes

Expected outcomes of the PhD project were to reveal challenges and opportunities of One Health institutionalisation and to produce lessons that can be learned from countries experiences. To achieve this, the PhD project produced six papers that analyse One Health institutionalisation from different angles (such as policy processes and organisational structures). This has been of interest for WP7 and has been discussed to ensure sustainable institutionalisation of the One Health approach. The findings of PhD project are interesting for all OHEJP partner institutes and organisations as it can facilitate the operationalisation of the One Health approach in relation to networks, cross-sector collaborations, political agenda setting and knowledge translation.

3.3.2. Expected scientific impact

Future research approaches can build on the knowledge produced by the dissertation, using the theoretical angles and advancing them. The dissertation focused on knowledge translation by drawing parallels between One Health networks and the knowledge transfer model by Liyanage et al. (2009). Using knowledge translation provided opportunities for understanding One Health communication and terminologies. It pointed out the benefits of further investigating these and other aspects within the knowledge transfer model. More in-depth investigations of different steps (or all steps simultaneously) of the knowledge transfer model could help understand ways to enhance coordination, communication, management, and the use of resources. For example, investigating awareness and the acquisition of knowledge can help to determine processes and benchmarks that identify 'appropriate or valuable knowledge', and to discover the ability of receivers to acquire the knowledge (Liyanage et al., 2009, p. 126). Further research should also elucidate the receivers' abilities to absorb new information by investigating how knowledge becomes useful. This could produce practical implications that can guide new One Health-related contributions to existing knowledge bases and establish the means to effective problem brokering. Further, evaluating knowledge transfer processes within and across institutions could help reveal problems that hinder the conveyance of information and data. This will help to work on challenges and embrace opportunities to strengthen and maintain knowledge translation within the One Health approach.

Additionally, the PhD project provides potential starting point for further social and political science research of the One Health approach.

3.3.3. Expected societal and policy impact

The results of the dissertation can be useful for all institutions and organisations that aim to work with a One Health approach. The dissertation provides practical knowledge on opportunities to implement the One Health approach, for example by way of establishing a One Health strategy or identifying and

engaging policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers to strengthen knowledge translation and political agenda setting. This can lead to strengthen the understanding of the One Health approach practically for each activity as well as institutionally, and it can promote heterophil collaboration, which strengthens innovation and cross-sector knowledge exchange. It can facilitate harmonisation of data gathering and analytical approaches, which helps to prevent redundant work among scientists from different sectors and facilitates the comparison of data, which is crucial for disease surveillance activities.

Further, the dissertation provides recommendations regarding the knowledge translation of scientific findings to policymakers and to the public. This can involve the engagement of the public into research activities and provide opportunity to popularise the One Health approach.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Research design

The One Health approach is more commonly known within the natural sciences, especially the veterinary sciences, than in the social or political sciences (Paper I). Hence, from a social science perspective, the One Health approach has yet to be studied extensively, which provided opportunity for this explorative study to investigate some institutional and political aspects of the One Health approach (Lapinski et al., 2015; Stebbins, 2001). The research process mirrors abductive reasoning through the entangled process of choosing methods, theories, and concepts under the influence of the empirical data that was gathered (Blaikie, 2007). The explorative study was based on mixed methods, where data was triangulated and several methodological approaches fed into each other. This enabled the identification of patterns within the data and revealed complementary traits that allowed generalisations to be drawn (Heale & Forbes, 2013).

Qualitative and quantitative approaches were used to gain insight into the One Health approach. Data was gathered sequentially, meaning that it was collected in successive periods (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). Initially, a literature review on the One Health approach was conducted to gain an overview of the current state of academic and practical knowledge. The literature search extended to a bibliometric analysis of the current state of One Health research. Two cases were then selected to investigate national-level One Health institutionalisation. The cases describe Swedish and Italian One Health practices and represent experts from national agencies and institutes who unveil institutional structures that promote or inhibit the implementation of the One Health approach. Experts are individuals who have knowledge that others do not, including specialised knowledge and skills in a particular area gathered through their occupation and experience (Meuser & Nagel, 2009). The interviewees included scientific and administrative experts, which made it possible to analyse and compare One Health institutionalisation across agencies and countries in-depth. A survey was subsequently launched, addressed to scientific and administrative experts in EU agencies, NGOs and national institutes within some EU countries together with Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. In the dissertation, research pertaining to 'Europe' usually refers to the countries included in the survey: the 23 EU member states plus Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom (see Table 4 for a complete list of countries). Data was gathered on science-led policy processes to identify One Health policy processes, networks, and agenda setting. The triangulation of the methods aided to

enhance the validity of the data, and the mixed method approach allowed the use of information gathered through one method to inform another. This approach provided a multifaceted view by employing methods that examined different national and international perspectives (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). Combined, each method contributed to answering the research question by providing insights from different perspectives, such as institutional and governmental processes, individual actors, their roles, and networks.

4.2. *Analysis of the literature*

The dissertation and papers are based on scientific and grey literature. Hence, both systematic and semi-systematic reviews of the literature were conducted (Snyder, 2019). For the semi-systematic literature reviews, platforms such as Web of Science, PubMed, Google Scholar and web searches were used. Google searches were usually employed to detect grey literature (e.g., EU reports, national and international surveillance reports, and other non-peer-reviewed publications). The aim was to identify and synthesise research to obtain an overview and deeper understanding of a topic.

For the systematic review, the literature was searched more methodically, using only peer-reviewed articles from the Web of Science and PubMed platforms together with pre-formulated inclusion and exclusion criteria. Search terms were formulated and, after the initial search, the literature was screened to remove duplicates or other literature not suiting the criteria.

Additionally, a bibliometric analysis was conducted to quantitatively link and visualise data produced by researchers revealing specific patterns and characteristics in terms of collaborations, networks as well as citations (Zupic & Čater, 2015). The analysis of academic features concentrated on publication trends, a co-citation network of scientific journals, co-citation network of authors, and co-occurrence of keywords. The bibliometric analysis contributed to an overview as well as describing and evaluating the published research. The statistical analysis was conducted with the bibliometrix package for the R programming language.

4.3. *Case selection*

The main focus of the study was Europe, specifically the EU, its member states, plus Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. The region provides a network of unique countries all facing health issues on the human–animal–environment interface. Those health issues can be similar, as for example how AMR concerns all countries. But they can also be distinct; for example, due to cooler northern or warmer southern climates. One Health-related challenges can be zoonotic diseases, AMR, food safety issues, climate change, environmental contamination, and many more (Garcia & Gostin, 2012). On the EU level, there are agencies tasked with tackling One Health challenges. The EFSA, EMA, ECDC, and European Environment Agency (EEA) are some of those agencies (Bronzwaer et al., 2022). Within European countries, there are usually specific national research institutes and government agencies involved in preventing and combating health threats, such as public health, veterinary, food and environment agencies (Mazet et al., 2014). European countries and the EU as a whole provide a comprehensive set of institutes, agencies and networks that coordinate interdisciplinary activities, such as outbreak management and surveillance activities (Belfroid et al., 2020; Bronzwaer et al., 2022; Jordana & Triviño-Salazar, 2020). In addition to the institutional and organisational aspects, the advising capacity of national and EU agencies to policymakers provided insight into One Health decision- and policymaking processes (Chatzopoulou, 2018).

To gain more specific insight, two countries, Sweden and Italy, were selected to serve as examples of how they tackled One Health issues. These two country cases allowed the investigation of a phenomenon, here the One Health approach, in different contexts and situations. They enabled the utilisation of knowledge that existed within the two cases (Yin, 2014). Each country case provided insights into specific institutional and political structures of their public health, veterinary, environment and food institutes.

Cases were selected based on convenience sampling strategy. The non-random sampling was used as the cases were easily accessible due to gatekeepers who facilitated access to the institutes under investigation in the countries. The sampling strategy is based on the judgement of the researcher and struggles with selection bias, meaning that other important cases may not be detected or excluded (Schreier, 2018). To avoid the unintentional exclusion of cases, the semi-systematic analysis of the literature provided information on the state and usage of the One Health approach within European countries. Additionally, the grey literature provided an overview of One Health-related policy and pandemic surveillance documents. The literature highlighted research activities (or the lack thereof) in Sweden and Italy relating to the One Health approach. Further, the assessment of the cases was based on a mapping of the 44 OHEJP partner agencies situated in the 22 EU member states (One Health EJP, 2021). This ensured that the institutes within the selected countries related their work to the One Health approach. One obvious limitation is the lack of an eastern European country case. Eastern European countries could have provided valuable knowledge on One Health institutionalisation, as the lack of literature relating to One Health in those countries indicates some of the challenges related to the implementation of the approach (Humboldt-Dachroeden et al., 2020). An eastern European country case could have provided lessons learned regarding challenges in implementing the One Health approach and could have potentially revealed how to prevent and overcome them.

4.4. Interviews

The interviews were designed to examine the institutional structures, practices, and networks within public health, veterinary, food, and environment institutes via a case-based qualitative analysis. The study was based on semi-structured, open-ended interviews. Thirteen interviews were conducted for the Swedish case, 19 for the Italian case. The interviewee profiles included experts from the public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors, who were engaged in national and international projects concerning One Health topics (see Table 2). Expert interviews were utilised, as they provided an effective tool for gathering technical and specific information (Bogner et al., 2009). Approximately three months were invested in collecting data for each case, six months total. Thirty-two interviews were conducted, which unveiled unique insight into One Health practices and outbreak-related operations. Variations in agency sizes and the availability of experts led to an uneven distribution of interviewees.

Table 1: Workplace and background of Swedish and Italian interviewees

SWEDEN		ITALY	
PUBLIC HEALTH AGENCY [N = 4]		NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF HEALTH [N = 11]	
1	Microbiology	1	Veterinarian
2	Epidemiology	2	Biology
3	Epidemiology	3	Chemistry
4	Epidemiology	4	Veterinary epidemiology
		5	Natural Science
		6	Human medicine
		7	Public health
		8	Veterinary medicine
		9	Molecular biology
		10	Molecular biology
		11	Veterinary medicine
NATIONAL VETERINARY INSTITUTE [N = 6]		REGIONAL VETERINARY INSTITUTES [N = 6]	
5	Finance	12	Veterinarian
6	Veterinary pathology	13	Biology
7	Veterinary epidemiology	14	Veterinary medicine
8	Epidemiology	15	Veterinary medicine
9	Research coordination	16	Veterinary epidemiology
10	Parasitology	17	Veterinary medicine
ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AGENCY [N = 1]		NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND RESEARCH [N = 1]	
11	Biology	18	Environmental Science
NATIONAL FOOD AGENCY [N = 1]		NOT APPLICABLE	
12	Microbiology		
13	Microbiology		
NO INTERVIEWS CONDUCTED [N = 0]		MINISTRY OF HEALTH [N = 1]	
		19	Veterinary medicine
	Total Swedish interviews: 13		Total Italian interviews: 19
Total interviews: 32			

A purposive sampling strategy was employed, which is a non-random sampling based on pre-existing knowledge of the cases (Schreier, 2018). Sampling was based on the best available knowledge, which was developed in the course of research stays in Sweden and Italy that enabled networking and exchange; through OHEJP-provided data regarding the consortium members in the two countries that specified their roles; and through web searches that identified additional experts in the public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors. Access to experts beyond the OHEJP consortium members

was needed, including to experts in regional veterinary institutes in Italy or to experts in environment institutes in Italy and Sweden. Hence, the snowball sampling strategy, where participants helped to identify other potential subjects among their acquaintances, was employed and the participants provided a useful source for contacts (Vallgård & Koch, 2008). These strategies strengthened the reliability and limited the unintentional exclusion of interviewees. This method proved useful, as it made it possible to approach people who were knowledgeable about specific issues relevant for the study.

The Swedish interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams or Skype for Business. The Italian interviews were conducted partly online and face-to-face. The latter were conducted in Rome with experts from the National Public Health Institute, and at the regional veterinary institutes in Brescia, Padova, Bologna, and Teramo.

4.4.1. Analytical approach

The interview recordings were transcribed, applying intelligent verbatim transcription. This means that filling words were not included in the transcriptions and grammar was corrected. The transcripts were then examined using the software NVivo Pro (version 12) via content analysis. Assarroudi et al. (2018) define content analysis as a systematic coding and categorising approach, suitable for larger data sets. This approach was used to determine trends and patterns among the words used, their relationships and structures, as well as discourses of communication. The NVivo software supported the process of coding and categorising themes.

Coding is a process whereby data are labelled and categorised by assigning different categories or themes to it. Open coding was applied to categorise key themes and identify patterns. Codes were assigned based on the interpretation of the data in the transcripts, sometimes assigning different codes to the same sentence. By categorising the codes, themes were established. This enabled an in-depth understanding of participants' perceptions and motivations.

4.5. Survey

An online survey entitled 'One Health governance survey' was conducted to provide data for a study of the institutionalisation of the One Health approach among different epistemological communities, both cross-country and cross-sector. The survey examined the political drivers and constraints for the integration of the One Health approach across Europe. Specifically, it aimed to illuminate how One Health principles are included in the policy- and decisionmaking processes of political actors and networks.

The survey target group consisted of policy actors from public health, veterinary, food, and environment institutes, and government agencies; ministries; NGOs; and EU agencies. Represented NGOs were, for example, the WHO and WOA. The EU agencies included the EFSA, EMA, and EEA (see Table 3).

Table 2: Workplaces of survey respondents

WORKPLACE				[N]
Veterinary institute				18
Public health institute				17
University				12
Food institute				12
Ministry (Ministries of Agriculture; Health; Education & Research)				7
NGO (WHO, WOA, ICARS*)				5
Interdisciplinary research institutes:				
Veterinary	Food	Environment	Agriculture	
x	x			4
	x	x	x	4
x	x	x		4**
x	x	x	x	3
x			x	2
Agriculture institute				2
EU agency (EFSA, EMA, EEA***)				4
Funding institute				1
Museum (natural history)				1
N/A				8
Total:				104

Source: Adapted from Humboldt-Dachroeden (2023)

* ICARS: International Centre for Antimicrobial Resistance Solutions

**One research institute also includes public health services

*** EMA: European Medicines Agency; EEA: European Environment Agency

A purposive sampling strategy was applied to target these experts. To avoid selection bias, the population was defined to include experts and policy actors in the public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors, employed in institutes, government agencies, and organisations in Europe. Here, the OHEJP provided a network of experts from 44 different government agencies, ministries, EU agencies, and NGOs. Via internal mailing lists, the survey was distributed to the OHEJP network members. Own searches for participants were also conducted, targeting experts working within relevant areas and sectors. Four rounds of follow-up emails were sent out, addressed to non-responders, which engaged more participants each time. The survey sample size concluded with 104 participants from four regions (western Europe, Nordic countries, southern Europe, and eastern Europe), from 20 EU and three non-EU, European countries (Norway, Switzerland, United Kingdom) (see Table 4). Among the regions, eastern European countries are least represented, with only one or two individuals participating per country. This is due to fewer contacts and lack of responses from eastern European respondents. With a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, the desired sample size would be 141 respondents. Nevertheless, the survey sample provides a good overview of different countries, experiences, and expertise.

Table 3: List of countries of survey respondents' residences

	COUNTRIES	[N]
Western Europe	United Kingdom	10
	Germany	9
	France	8
	The Netherlands	7
	Belgium	5
	Austria	4
	Switzerland	3
	Ireland	2
Nordic countries	Sweden	10
	Denmark	8
	Norway	3
	Finland	3
Southern Europe	Italy	9
	Portugal	6
	Spain	1
Eastern Europe	Hungary	2
	Lithuania	2
	Bulgaria	1
	Czech Republic	1
	Estonia	1
	Latvia	1
	Poland	1
	Romania	1
	N/A	6
	Total	104
	Countries: 23	
	EU countries: 20	
	European countries: 3	

Source: Adapted from Humboldt-Dachroeden (2023)

4.5.1. *Analytical approach*

The survey respondents represented experts who provided their subjective perspective and expertise to the questions, based on their work environment, the topics they work with, and their experience with the One Health approach. This offered general information about their countries, as the questionnaire contained specific questions relating to their country of residence. While the respondents indirectly and directly depict their workplaces, their perspectives are not restricted to the workplace, as they might also draw on their experiences within networks, memberships, collaborations, and other activities.

The survey analysis was divided into two parts; first, the qualitative and quantitative analyses are described. The former contained the analysis of the open-ended questions relating to comments and

elaborations made by the respondents. Demographics and answers to the open-ended questions were entered into NVivo Pro (version 12) to conduct a thematic content analysis. Separate analyses were conducted, depending on the aim of the papers. The coding process established relevant themes, which were subsequently reviewed to ensure the consistent and appropriate categorisation of codes into the themes.

The quantitative analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Software (version 27). The general response rate and response rates for sub-populations of survey respondents from different European regions were calculated. The closed-ended questions were fed into the software to analyse descriptive statistics of respondents' characteristics in terms of countries, workplace, and areas of work. This included some measures of central tendencies. Independent t-tests were used to determine potential significant differences between the means of sub-groups of the survey population.

5. Scientific Results and Discussion

The research for this dissertation explored the implementation of the One Health approach in institutional settings. To do so, the following research question was established:

What are the key institutional drivers and constraints on the effective implementation of the One Health approach?

The dissertation is based on five articles and one chapter, which address the research question from different angles, allowing for different theoretical, methodological, and empirical perspectives. The individual findings of the papers are presented coherently by linking overlapping and connected topics. The papers address institutional and political aspects in relation to the One Health approach. Institutional aspects are structures and procedures of government and research institutes. Political aspects relate to the science–policy interface, including governance, political attention, agenda setting, and policymaking. The studies contribute to the literature by adding knowledge about the implementation of the One Health approach on an institutional level, and they give insight into agenda setting and knowledge translation processes. The dissertation provides some practical implications, such as lessons learned via the case study, which are relevant for institutions and agencies that (aim to) implement the One Health approach.

The findings of the dissertation stretch from practical research-related to organisational and political aspects, making the findings interesting for scientists, policy actors, and individuals within national government agencies as well as national and international institutes and organisations working with the One Health approach. Concretely, the dissertation contributes to the fundamental understanding of the One Health approach, knowledge translation processes, and institutional as well as political decisionmaking practices. The challenges and opportunities of One Health institutionalisation that were revealed through the research project can contribute to enhancing existing and future One Health activities. The findings can impact local communities by engaging them and establishing contextual conditions for the One Health approach. Practically, One Health communication and education in schools, universities, and among scientists can further strengthen the understanding of cross-cutting health threats.

In the following, the general findings of the papers and their connections are discussed under four sub-headings. Under the first, One Health-related sectors and disciplines as well as governments, government agencies, and how their set-up affects collaboration are discussed. The second sub-chapter addresses knowledge translation among scientists, between scientists and policymakers, and between scientists and the public. It provides some insight into the concepts of the policy entrepreneur and problem broker together with potential avenues for translating scientific findings. The third sub-chapter focuses on managing One Health in relation to leadership, relationships, and networks. The last sub-chapter ends with a discussion of the limitations and reflections on theoretical and methodological choices, and implications as well as possibilities for future research.

a. Chapter 1: Institutional silos, sectors and disciplines

5.1.1. About the sectors of One Health

In the scientific context, the One Health approach is mostly known and used among veterinary scientists, and something of a monopoly has been established (Paper I). On the other hand, the environmental sciences are not as engaged, both due to a lack of initiation and invitation. This two-sided challenge represents on the one hand scientists at the public health, veterinary, and food agencies, who find it difficult to engage with scientists from environment institutes due to lack of knowledge on who to involve, and not perceiving a need to connect. On the other hand, scientists at the environment institutes do not find thematic overlaps and, if common themes do exist, they lack information on who to contact (Papers I–III). However, environmental aspects and conditions have been described in the literature as important for tackling many health-related issues (Jones et al., 2008; Redford et al., 2021; Zinsstag et al., 2018). Environmental conditions can help to predict stress as well as risks, and the environment affects humans and animals through a variety of pathways. They can be directly related to beneficial or adverse effects for humans, animals, the ecosystem, and its biodiversity (Paper III). This also includes plant health, which has received little attention in One Health projects and activities thus far (Andrivon et al., 2021).

The public health disciplines are frequently represented and engaged within One Health activities (Papers I–VI). This includes public health professionals but does not always expand to medical professionals working in hospitals (Paper VI). Relations among veterinary and public health institutes exist, and they are often good (Papers II & VI). Agriculture, food, and climate are often categorised under the public health, veterinary, and environment sectors. An example of categorising sectors is illustrated in Figure 9, where disciplines are displayed within their circle. Each circle displays a sector. The listed disciplines are not conclusive, as there are other topics that could be added or recognised as part of already established categories (e.g., biostatistics, behavioural medicine, toxicology). The sectors overlap with one another (see explanation of sectors in section 1.2). One Health is displayed in the middle to illustrate its connection to all sectors.

Figure 5: Public health, veterinary, as well as environment sectors and their disciplines of the One Health approach

In addition to the public health, veterinary, and environment sectors, there is another sector that directly and indirectly affects all other sectors and their disciplines: the social sciences. Within the One Health approach, a stronger social science presence could possibly provide tools and techniques to assess and appreciate contextual factors that aid in the creation of projects and activities (Papers I & V). The sector is crucial, as it can contribute to an understanding of societal contexts, economic, and behavioural aspects, and it can be used to understand policymaking processes, institutions, and networks (Papers I–V). Figure 10 includes the social science sector and its disciplines, surrounding the public health, veterinary, and environment sectors. This aims to illustrate the potential disciplines with which the social sciences can contribute, as well as the cross-cutting nature of this sector.

Figure 6: Public health, veterinary, environment and social science sectors and their disciplines of the One Health approach

Including different perspectives and tools of the social sciences can benefit One Health activities and shine some light into the black box of One Health policymaking (Degeling et al., 2015; Lapinski et al., 2015; Michalon, 2020). For One Health policymaking, the social sciences can assist in mediating and brokering between scientists and politicians by providing insight into policy processes and political institutions (Papers IV–VI). Further, the social science sector can reveal contextual as well as behavioural aspects underlying to One Health issues. Contributing to clarifying contextual aspects is to define the One Health approach in the beginning – as a fundament – of projects or activities. Because how the approach is defined depends on the context of where the One Health approach is implemented (Papers II & V). Clarifying and defining the approach can prevent the word ‘One Health’ from merely becoming a trend or ‘buzzword’⁴ (Paper V). It can facilitate the implementation and institutionalisation of the One Health approach by establishing the frame, scope, context, and capabilities.

5.1.2. Governments and government agencies

On the local and national levels, the sectors on the human–animal–environment interface are usually represented by government agencies, such as public health, veterinary, food, and environment agencies; by universities; and by other research institutes. The government agencies are mandated by legislation which defines their agendas and priorities. Within a government agency, there is often a

⁴ From One Health governance survey 2021. Respondent’s workplace: Research institute in areas of agriculture, environment, and food.

fruitful environment that allows for the exchange of information and performance of interdisciplinary activities (Paper II). Engaging in activities across agencies can, however, be a challenge. The clash of interests due to different agendas and priorities, data security issues, competition, or lack of resources can impede cross-sector collaboration and communication (Papers II–VI). This is why the sectors are often referred to as silos. The coordination of activities, collaboration, and communication are easier within a silo, as there are clear common objectives and themes. Bridging to another silo entails more complex coordination, as potentially distinct interests and objectives must be addressed. Obviously, connecting three or even more sectors presents an even more complex web of agendas, interests, and priorities, all of which must be accommodated. Nevertheless, it is important to have those sectors with their respective focus and perspective. They provide specific knowledge that can be and is used for political decisionmaking (van Thiel et al., 2012). However, a mindful division of the topics within the sectors together with a cautious establishment of additional sectors is crucial (Paper VI). Being mindful and cautious helps to identify connections and complementary knowledge that can be important for decision- and policymaking (van Thiel et al., 2012). The case study provides two examples of how two topics are categorised differently among government agencies: In Italy, the National Institute of Health deals with food safety, but the veterinary institutes also work with certain food safety issues. In Sweden, in contrast, food safety is handled by the National Food Agency, a stand-alone agency. Further, water-related issues are categorised within the Institute for Environmental Protection and Research in Italy, whereas matters related to drinking-water are dealt with by the National Food Agency in Sweden, the Environmental Protection Agency taking care of other water-related topics (see Table 5) (Paper VI).

Table 4: Italian and Swedish agencies responsible for food safety and water-related issues

	GOVERNMENT AGENCIES	FOOD SAFETY	WATER
Italy	National Institute of Health	✓	✗
	Veterinary institutes	✓	✗
	Institute for Environmental Protection and Research	✗	✓
Sweden	Public Health Agency	✗	✗
	National Veterinary Institute	✗	✗
	Environmental Protection Agency	✗	✓
	National Food Agency	✓	✓

This depicts an example of two distinct government approaches to categorising food safety and water-related issues in different sectors. Of course, the categorisation is not static and can change in the future with the election of new governments that transform agendas, ministries, and agencies. Hence, the categorisation of the sectors can vary as disciplines might be combined or split under different ministries and institutes, affecting the mandates and tasks of the agencies or institutes. This also affects collaboration and funding opportunities. The effects on governance must be taken into account when establishing services, agendas, and distributing responsibilities to enable multifaceted partnerships, cross-fertilisation, and sustainable approaches.

Different countries obviously have different arrangements of government structures and divisions of services under the ministries. Some European countries (e.g., Germany, Belgium) have federal systems where the central government does not hold all the power, instead sharing it with the regional authorities (Papers IV & V). Along with increased bureaucracy, this can lead to disconnected governing approaches of national, regional, and local authorities (Paper VI). The different government systems – as well as under which ministry the public services are mandated – can have implications for the resources available, the power or influence of the institute, and how they operate and respond (Azfar et al., 2004). For example, the research in Paper V points towards some well-working arrangements of government agencies to tackle AMR (e.g., DANMAP in Denmark). Paper IV however, presents remaining challenges that the fight against AMR still faces. The challenges might be due to the lack of perceived urgency, judging AMR as a creeping crisis (Engström, 2021; Munkholm et al., 2021). Additionally, Paper IV describes how intricate institutional contexts cause issues, where multiple ministries and government agencies work on different aspects of AMR on the national level. The institutions do not always align their work (e.g., through similar analytical approaches and data harmonisation to make data comparable), which adds to the information complexity that compromises cross-sector collaboration and communication. To prevent information complexity, national governments must consider interconnections when creating government agencies. For this, governments must establish criteria that account for the needs of those agencies to allow for transparency and manageability (Paper VI) (van Thiel et al., 2012).

5.1.3. Geographical silos

In addition to the challenges that can arise with establishing agencies and the distribution of topics, there are geographic distinctions that can impact agency productivity. For example, the geographic proximity of agencies within a country can facilitate collaboration (Paper II). Across countries, it can be more difficult to maintain such collaboration, as effort and funding is required (Papers V & VI). For instance, there are few co-citations and One Health-related publications of authors from eastern European countries, indicating little interaction (Paper I). Western (and especially Nordic) countries seem more inclined to implement the One Health approach than eastern European countries (Paper V). There can be many reasons for this, and the process can change as the One Health approach gains popularity and more international research funds support projects with a One Health perspective (Paper I). The scarcity of eastern European countries within interdisciplinary research projects and the lack of data from those countries for international surveillance activities is a challenge for the One Health approach, as it leads to a fragmented picture, making data comparisons, disease prevention, and tracing measures more difficult (Boqvist et al., 2018). The eastern European countries and the countries working together with them would benefit from collaborations in terms of cross-fertilisation, knowledge creation, and sharing. To establish a comprehensive One Health approach, these disparities and differences should be evaluated and approached within institutes as well as by decision- and policymakers (Papers IV–VI). Policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers are actors who can be employed to tackle this disconnect, as they can use their skills to create networks and establish connections (Paper VI). Education promoting the One Health approach throughout the working lives of scientists can contribute to the dismantling of (geographical) silos by emphasising the cross-sector and cross-country connectedness of One Health-related topics (Paper II).

5.1.4. Bridging silos during outbreaks

Working together across disciplines and sectors can be particularly effective during ‘war times’⁵; that is, periods when there is a disease outbreak (Paper II). During such war times, which can involve food-borne disease outbreaks like Salmonellosis or Campylobacteriosis (Paper II) or infectious diseases like COVID-19 (Papers II & VI), funds are more rapidly allocated to tackle outbreaks, and cross-sector coordination is facilitated. During one food-borne disease outbreak⁶ in Sweden, however, the National Food Agency and Public Health Agency clashed over different agendas and priorities: the National Food Agency with interest for the food industry and economy; the Public Health Agency with interest for public health (Papers II & VI). Such conflicting agendas and priorities must be considered when establishing One Health surveillance and response activities. At the same time, different orientations can also be complementary and result in strong, knowledge-sharing networks (Papers II & V).

Additionally, in Sweden and Italy, the tackling of disease outbreaks revealed different perspectives between the medical, veterinary, and public health sectors; where the medical perspective usually focuses on the individual, the veterinary and public health perspectives can include both individual and population-wide perspectives. These differing perspectives can become a point of contention regarding the respective importance among practitioners and scientists (Paper VI). During the COVID-19 pandemic, Swedish and Italian scientists highlighted the value of both perspectives. In these two countries, the veterinary agencies have demonstrated their significant contributions to tackling the pandemic. Public health laboratories and hospitals usually have less capacity, processing smaller numbers of samples. Conversely, veterinary laboratories are used to test multitudes of samples, applying a herd or population approach (Papers II & VI). In addition to the laboratory capacity, combining the expertise of public health and veterinary scientists on SARS viruses, which is a subject studied in both fields, has contributed to improving practices regarding diagnosis, therapies, and the treatment of COVID-19-related maladies (Paper VI) (Fenollar et al., 2021). The environment institutes also contributed to investigating the spread of COVID-19; in Italy, for example, studies were conducted to determine the presence of the virus in sewage (Paper III) (La Rosa et al., 2021). Hence, all sectors related to the human–animal–environment interface were utilised in some manner to contain the spread of COVID-19 or to inform about it. A One Health approach was institutionalised as the countries invested effort in developing cross-sector activities and processes – whether intentionally or unintentionally *One Health*. The urgency of the outbreak facilitated the allocation of funds that were helpful to link sectors, work together, and share knowledge. The Italian case, however, displayed some persisting difficulties across sectors (Paper VI). The veterinary agencies responsible for analysing the swabs for COVID-19 experienced challenges when working with medical doctors in hospitals. The main claim that was voiced concerned the lack of knowledge of medical doctors about the work and expertise of veterinarians. Unfortunately, within the PhD project, medical doctors working in hospitals were not interviewed and could therefore not provide their perspective, which would have been worthwhile. The reason for the difficulties among veterinarians and medical doctors might be rooted in different values and hierarchical thinking, which should be addressed to enable a levelled and fruitful environment for future collaboration (Huth et al., 2019). This can be approached via training and the education of scientists, explaining the meaning and actors involved in tackling multifaceted health issues (Papers II & VI).

⁵ From interview study 2020. Respondent’s workplace: Veterinary institute, Sweden.

⁶ Mentioned during interviews with Swedish experts (2020).

The Swedish and Italian cases provide examples of the lessons learned in terms of how veterinary, public health, food (and sometimes environment) institutes communicate, collaborate, and coordinate One Health-related activities (Papers II & VI). Concretely, lessons can be learned about cross-sector meetings concerning outbreaks, One Health networks, and collaborative approaches to tackle disease outbreaks (e.g., Salmonellosis, Campylobacteriosis, and COVID-19) (Papers II & VI).

b. Chapter 2: Learning new languages

Language and the translation of knowledge plays a tremendous role for the One Health approach, and it can address different actors and sectors (Papers II, IV, V, & VI). In this context, knowledge translation can contribute to the learning of new languages, 'languages' in the sense of different terminologies and the specialist jargon with which research, operations, methods, analytical approaches, and other specific issues are communicated. This provides opportunity for different actors to get to know and contribute to the One Health approach. Some actors were identified within the papers and will be presented in three different dimensions that depict knowledge translation among scientists, between scientists and policymakers, and between scientists and the public. Each of these dimensions provides potential ways to overcome translation issues, which can have practical implications for implementing the One Health approach.

5.2.1. Knowledge translation among scientists

The first dimension addresses knowledge translation **among scientists** within different disciplines and sectors. Communication, data sharing, and understanding one another are key aspects of knowledge translation. The public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors all have their own terminologies, methods, and analytical approaches, and while they overlap, they do not always align (Papers II, IV, & V) (Mateus et al., 2022). Different technologies and analytical methods can produce results that are difficult and sometimes impossible to compare (Paper II). This provides challenges, both on national and international levels, when working together on cross-sector health issues, research projects, and when carrying out disease surveillance activities. Such difficulties can be in the form of fundamental communication-related issues when scientists talk with one another about the same issue from their respective sector-related perspectives, the difficulties being due to different terminologies. Methods and analytical approaches used in different sectors also reflect their own language, because using different methods and analytical approaches for the same issue (e.g., Salmonellosis surveillance) can lead to different interpretations and difficulties when comparing findings. Hence, harmonising data can at least to some extent facilitate the comparison of data, which is crucial when investigating health threats that are able to cross borders (Papers II–IV). It can also enhance the efficient use of data, as similar samples or data are often gathered across the different sectors. Streamlining and communicating data can prevent the unnecessary duplication of efforts (Paper VI). Establishing cross-sector networks supported by strong and open-minded leadership can save resources by facilitating the exchange and brokering of knowledge across sectors (Papers IV & VI). Tools such as glossaries should be shared within networks, and they can help to clarify the terms and terminologies used in other sectors (Papers II & V).

A One Health strategy on an institutional level that problematises and defines each specific One Health topic will further help to clarify roles, responsibilities, and the expectations held to one another (Papers I, V, & VI). This can especially have positive implications for the environment sector as their role and potential contributions become clear, which could motivate future collaborations (Papers II, V, & VI). Further, capacity building in terms of scientist training and education can facilitate the learning of new

languages and jargon, by promoting the understanding of One Health surveillance techniques and more generally by specifying the One Health approach in practice. Capacity building constitutes an important aspect of the One Health approach, as reflected in the high number of One Health networks reporting on it (Khan et al., 2018). Capacity building refers to individual development in terms of equipping scientists with skills and access to information, knowledge, and training. Ideally, this will lead to personal development and enable performance as well as adaption to new knowledge and contexts (Boyko et al., 2012). Paper V identifies the influencing factor ‘lack of context’ that typically hampers the knowledge translation process. Engagement with social, political, and economic scientists will prove fruitful, as their contributions can address this issue by using tools and expertise to unravel contextual and cultural aspects. While natural scientists might be somewhat accustomed to the One Health approach, this is a novel notion for many social scientists (Papers I & VI). Building bridges across the sectors and tackling homophily will facilitate knowledge sharing and learning. This can contribute to an enhanced understanding of the world as an interconnected web while acknowledging local, societal, and political realities (Papers I & VI) (Craddock & Hinchliffe, 2015; Lapinski et al., 2015). Figure 11 summarises knowledge translation actions that can be taken among scientists, as well as their potential implications.

Figure 7: Knowledge translation between scientists – the implications for the One Health approach

5.2.2. Knowledge translation between scientists and policymakers

The second dimension addresses issues of knowledge translation **among scientists and policymakers** (e.g., bureaucrats, politicians). ‘Lack of common language among scientists and policymakers’ is an influencing factor interfering with the knowledge translation process (Paper V). Scientists who want to share their knowledge (scientific findings) are often faced with difficulties in their interactions with policymakers (Mateus et al., 2022). Or even one step before this: When seeking to catch their attention (Paper V). Policymakers often lack a background in the natural sciences and, in the same way, scientists do not necessarily have any training in the dissemination of science to non-scientists. The inability to break down complex scientific information and to create a ‘compelling narrative’⁷ can lead to misunderstandings and render it impossible to convey the importance of a specific issue (Paper V). The fact that One Health issues often span several disciplines and sectors contributes to the difficulty of expressing an issue coherently and making it readily understandable. Education and training in research communication can better equip scientists with the tools necessary to disseminate their research findings. Confident and eloquent expressions when sharing scientific findings within policy communities can help scientists to advocate and lobby for their topic and increase the likelihood of catching political attention (Papers IV & V). By doing so, they can become policy entrepreneurs, using their scientific expertise and storytelling competencies to translate knowledge (Paper II) (Stone, 2019).

⁷ From One Health governance survey 2021. Respondent’s workplace: World Health Organization.

Problem brokers can also be research communicators and help to frame scientific findings comprehensibly, as they are able to understand and speak the scientific and political languages (Rushmer et al., 2019).

Considering the One Health approach generally, many problems are already clearly outlined and solutions have been proposed, such as conceptual frameworks, guides, or references to support One Health research, policies and implementation (e.g., Coker et al., 2011; FAO et al., 2008; Lebov et al., 2017; Rüegg et al., 2018) (Papers I, II, IV, & V). However, political awareness is scarce and policy communities often struggle to generate interest (Connolly, 2017) (Papers II & V). This indicates areas where policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers can be employed to facilitate the contact between scientific and bureaucratic knowledge and to communicate successfully with politicians (Papers II & IV). Here, policy entrepreneurs who employ the networker strategy and know how to exploit networks can use their connections to inform policymakers of problems (Stone, 2019). The problems that require attention fuel the problem stream; and when the policy and politics windows also align, it can stimulate innovation in terms of methodologies, technologies, and analytical approaches (Kingdon, 2014; Rogers, 2003). Capturing political attention can have implications for scientists working with the One Health approach, potentially resulting in policy change and increased funding for One Health-related research. Increased awareness of the One Health approach and the issues it addresses can entail a more widespread use of the One Health term in strategic reports (Paper I); for example, the European Commission adopted the 'European One Health Action Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance' (European Commission, 2017). Mentioning One Health in the title and body of the document sends a clear signal to the EU member states, demonstrating the EU's initiative and encouraging the use of the One Health approach.

Paper V has presented processes that can lead to policy change, including the roles and abilities of different actors. International actors such as those coming from EU agencies (the ECDC, EFSA and the European Medicines Agency) were perceived as important to pushing One Health policies forward, and they can also act as policy entrepreneurs (Papers IV & V). Interestingly, based on the lack of co-citation networks of authors, there does not seem to be much scientific One Health-related exchange among these agencies (Paper I). The EFSA and ECDC have a memorandum of understanding to cooperate on common issues, explicitly mentioning the One Health approach (EFSA & ECDC, 2021). The bibliometric analysis indicates how greater effort should be invested in using each other's knowledge via co-authoring collaborations or by referencing one another (Paper I). Such increased mutual cross-fertilisation can influence policies relating to One Health issues, as they in fact advise and hence indirectly influence decisions made by the European Commission (Chatzopoulou, 2018; Wood, 2018). Establishing transdisciplinary One Health Research and Innovation governance, as suggested by Bronzwaer et al. (2022), could possibly aid the translation of knowledge between the agencies and set a research agenda that facilitates cross-sector collaboration. The Quadripartite were also perceived as important actors, especially due to the potentials lying in the organisations' combined forces and because of their prestige (Paper V). Building on this, the Quadripartite should identify policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers within their organisations who utilise their storytelling ability to translate knowledge, creating powerful and compelling narratives to inform policymakers (Stone, 2019). Above all, national agencies were recognised to be the most important actors to push One Health policies forward, which is plausible as the government agencies (evidence producers) are indirectly involved in government policymaking (evidence users) (Papers IV & V). Figure 12 summarises

the potential actions that can be taken to foster knowledge translation among scientists and policymakers, as well as the implications this might have for the One Health approach.

Figure 8: Knowledge translation between scientists and policymakers – the implications for the One Health approach

5.2.3. Knowledge translation between scientists and the public

Lastly, the third dimension examines knowledge translation between **scientists and the public**. The public impacts and is affected by their environment, their own health, as well as the health of animals and ecosystems. The characteristics of different communities – of how society is built and governed – are crucial for preventing, mitigating, and combating health threats. This has been emphasised in the definition of the One Health approach by the One Health High-Level Expert Panel (WHO, 2022a). However, there is often a disconnect between scientists and those communities and societies. The determinants of health address some of these connections, focusing especially on the people, societies, as well as the communities and the environment in which they live (Barton & Grant, 2006). The Determinants of Health Model (see Figure 3) lacks a specific ecosystem perspective, including animals. Yet the model provides a valuable knowledge base for the One Health approach in relation to the interconnectedness of individuals, communities, and their socioeconomic, cultural, and environmental conditions (Barton & Grant, 2006).

To disseminate knowledge, researchers mostly publish their findings in scientific journals that rarely reach the public. However, the communication to the public can be important to move from theory to practise (Senabre Hidalgo et al., 2021). It can activate the politics stream, in which the public mood is a crucial element for setting agendas (Kingdon, 2014). Disseminating scientific findings to the public can make them aware of an issue, stimulate discussion, and can pressure policymakers (Paper II). Similar to communication issues among scientists and policymakers, breaking down complex One Health topics remains an obstacle in communications with the public (Mateus et al., 2022). Training in research communication or employing research communicators and problem brokers can facilitate the translation of knowledge and popularise science. Scientists can engage with the public via their research projects, engaging, welcoming, and encouraging the public to take part if the project allows. Public participation, such as citizen science or the co-creation of science, can intrigue the public, make them more aware of the One Health approach, and reveal the societal and contextual determinants of health (Paper IV) (Senabre Hidalgo et al., 2021). Including the public in One Health-related research can lead to more local One Health activities and projects (Paper VI). If public participation is not possible, scientists can engage with the public in other ways, such as research fairs and festivals, social media, TV news, radio, and newspaper articles (Ross-Hellauer et al., 2020). A broad audience can be reached in this manner, enhancing knowledge about specific One Health topics and the whole approach in general (Paper IV). An enhanced understanding of the One Health approach among the

general public can trigger discussions and initiate action on the political level (Papers II & VI) (Haxton et al., 2015).

The One Health approach can also be brought to the public by implementing it in school education. This can give children the chance to become familiar with the approach already from a young age, which can enhance their knowledge about One Health, possibly even shaping their future education decisions (Paper II). A study of sustainability education showed that children who learn about topics relating to sustainability in school have an impact on their parents and their consumer habits (Walker, 2017). As Figure 13 illustrates, knowledge translation between scientists and the public can have positive implications in terms of generally raising knowledge about specific One Health topics relevant for a specific area or context and by shaping public opinion and attracting political attention to those issues.

Figure 9: Knowledge translation between scientists and the public – the implications for the One Health approach

c. Chapter 3: Managing One Health

Individuals and groups of people who inspire and lead are important drivers for the One Health approach. They must have the ability to steer through complex national and international systems, being conscious of needs, interests, priorities of states, governments, institutes, and organisations (Stephen & Stemshorn, 2016). This chapter scrutinises the opportunities available to leadership and leaders to drive the One Health approach forward. It examines the role and importance of relationships, including the nature of close relationships, their opportunities, and pitfalls for the One Health approach, and the potential to form relationships with new, previously unknown connections.

5.3.1. The role of leadership

In the context of this dissertation, leaders are individuals who lead scientific projects and networks. They can be policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers. However, policy entrepreneurs, problem brokers, and leaders are not interchangeable terms. Problem brokers have limited functions with respect to agenda setting. They usually operate in the preceding steps, framing a problem and making an issue understandable (Knaggård, 2015). Similarly, policy entrepreneurs work towards framing a problem and go further to suggest policy changes. Some of the skills of leaders go even further than that, as they possess more resources to make policy innovations (Capano & Galanti, 2021).

To establish and maintain collaborations within networks and scientific projects, there is a need for leaders with decisionmaking skills who guide, enable innovations, and are trustworthy (Papers IV–VI) (Rogers, 2003; Stokols et al., 2008). A leader must be able to problematise and define specific One Health issues to establish clear goals and objectives (Paper V). In the following, problematising specific One Health issues and the opportunities they entail will be described using the AMR example. Paper III outlined how Denmark demonstrated collaborative processes that problematise AMR. The DANMAP

report includes information, data, and knowledge from different sectors and has explicitly mentioned how implementing cross-sector monitoring and surveillance and engaging different sectors is based on motivated leadership (Papers III & V). However, while One Health approaches such as the Danish approach to AMR surveillance provide a good example, they cannot always be easily translated to other contexts, such as to countries or regions like the EU (Papers IV & V). Projects, programmes, activities, interventions, and measures that work on a local level might not be translatable to other local or global contexts – and vice versa. Activities must be adapted to specific circumstances, preferably already in the planning stages (Papers IV–VI). For example, implementing AMR stewardship programmes must consider the many actors who are affected and involved who have different aims and priorities. Additionally, microbes can easily cross state borders, meaning that AMR should not only be treated within countries but also – and ideally – in partnerships, collaborations, and networks with other countries (Paper IV). Apart from national actors, there are also multiple EU agencies and NGOs working with different aspects of AMR. Hence, leaders should facilitate among sectors and create inclusive networks to connect and create One Health activities that include all relevant actors (Paper V). The knowledge produced within such networks must be exploited to foster cooperation and communication (Papers IV & V). The aims and priorities of different actors must be accounted for and addressed to avoid miscommunication and shortcomings regarding mitigation and preventing the spread of diseases (Papers II & IV). Some international approaches, like the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance, which is a global funding coordinator, have successfully provided resources to collaborate on tackling AMR (Papers IV & V). Interdisciplinary projects like this facilitate cross-sector collaboration. Such projects can foster an understanding (and appreciation) of the counterpart's work (Papers II & VI).

However, combating AMR on an international level remains a challenge (Paper IV). This might be due to challenges in associating knowledge, which means conveying scientific information to the policymakers they find plausible and relatable (Papers IV & V). To tackle such challenges, engaging experts from the social, political, and economic sciences can aid in associating knowledge by using their methodological and analytical tools to assess circumstances and contexts. They can provide knowledge on contexts and policy processes from the local to the global levels, which can complement knowledge from the medical and natural sciences (Paper IV). Hence, engaging social, political, and economic experts can potentially induce innovation, as it allows for tailored, sustainable approaches (Papers IV–VI). Here, leaders must connect experts from the social, political, and natural sciences within networks to enable knowledge sharing. Based on this knowledge, leaders can then problematise issues and broker between sectors to establish relationships among the scientific and political sectors and to convey the scientific information comprehensibly to policymakers (Papers V & VI) (Rogers, 2003; Tasselli et al., 2015). This is the setting for problem brokers and policy entrepreneurs, who can use their skills to promote, convince, and even persuade policy- and decisionmakers (Papers II, IV, & VI). The focus should also be on using already existing stewardship programmes and frameworks for implementing as well as evaluating AMR (and other One Health) activities, and learning from studies that describe specific country cases (e.g., Jani et al., 2021; Lebov et al., 2017; Paternoster et al., 2017; Rüegg et al., 2018) in terms of their experiences with implementing the One Health approach (Papers I, II, & IV).

5.3.2. Close and distant relationships

Relationships, personal relationships in particular, are essential for the One Health approach, as they facilitate communication and make collaboration easier (Papers V & VI). Relationships promote the

implementation and effectiveness of activities, as shown by the collaborations among Swedish agencies on One Health-related topics as well as the collaboration of Danish institutes and industry on AMR (Papers II & III). Here, trust is necessary to carry out One Health activities and seems to ensure reliability subjectively (Papers IV & V). However, relationships are often confined to the borders of one's one epistemic culture and work environment. There are usually strong ties among actors, as they invest time and emotion in establishing the relationship (Rogers, 2003). This can lead to homophily and entail the exclusion of relevant actors and perspectives (Papers I & VI). Homophily describes the phenomenon whereby similar individuals (e.g., in terms of age, gender, work topic, education, values, beliefs, etc.) group together (McPherson et al., 2001). To combat homophily, establishing a One Health strategy within institutes that define the scope of activities and projects can help to determine relevant perspectives and actors who must come together (Paper VI). Leaders should clarify objectives as well as scope, ensuring the mapping of stakeholders in the design stage of the One Health activity (Paper VI) (Bordier et al., 2021; Mazet et al., 2014). In so doing, leaders can facilitate cross-sector connections and promote heterophily. This would encourage actors to engage with individuals with whom they have no prior relations (creating weak ties), which can facilitate new connections, information sharing, and innovation (Paper VI) (Rogers, 2003). Papers II and VI highlighted how seeking weak ties requires the availability and knowledge of where to find contact information. Institutions (e.g., government agencies, research institutes) should provide easy access to contact information. This will help to address collaboration shortcomings and avoid the exclusion of relevant actors, such as the oft-neglected actors from the environment sector (Papers I–III). It will also facilitate the inclusion of actors from the social and political sectors (Papers I, IV, V, & VI). Another possibility that can strengthen the collaboration of stakeholders from different sectors is to establish environments that facilitate knowledge sharing, such as interdisciplinary conferences, meetings, workshops, or summer schools (Papers I, II, & VI). Policy entrepreneurs and the problem brokers who are in such network environments can use or expand the networks to go from knowledge sharing to translation. The intermediaries can be used as brokers to connect sectors and actors. Additionally, there is already existing literature, guidance, and advice on establishing comprehensive One Health projects and activities as well as cross-sector and interdisciplinary collaborations, which can be used and adapted (Papers I & IV).

d. Chapter 4: Outcomes

The findings of the PhD project resulted in five scientific articles and one chapter. The papers follow a logic in terms of how they build on each other and the methods used. Figure 5 illustrates this by indicating the methods used in the papers and how they are connected by two pathways that show how the knowledge produced complements the next paper.

Pathway 1: Paper I gives practical insight into the scientific field of One Health and provides knowledge on institutional and research-related challenges together with the thematic issues of the approach. Papers II and VI are both based on interview studies. The knowledge in Paper I regarding institutional challenges is picked up in both articles. Paper II focuses on the case of Swedish public health, veterinary, food and environment agencies and how they institutionalise One Health. Paper VI builds further on the same and expands on the coordination and government structures in Swedish and Italian agencies. Papers II and VI informed the survey study, which led to the investigation of more underlying political structures within the individual institutes (Paper V).

Pathway 2: Paper III provides insights into thematic issues by specifically addressing a single sector in the human–animal–environment interface: the environment sector. This paper highlights the importance of the environment sector by investigating AMR and other environmental conditions that impact health. Both the bibliometric analysis (Paper I) and the literature review (Paper III) indicate challenges for the environment sector and the governance of the One Health approach. This informed the survey study, which elaborates on the role of governance, agenda setting, and policymaking, which was the basis for Papers IV and V. Paper IV picks up the topic of One Health governance in relation to AMR, while Paper V addresses national institutional and political aspects that impact the implementation of the One Health approach.

Figure 10: Pathways 1 and 2 displaying how papers are connected via methods

6. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

The dissertation set out to answer *what the key institutional drivers and constraints on the effective implementation of the One Health approach are.*

The dissertation arrives at three overarching themes: First, there are institutional barriers for implementing the One Health approach. The main barriers that the dissertation investigated are silo working, agendas, and government agency set-ups. Government agencies can be fragmented and, to approach this, governments must determine clear criteria when establishing ministries and government agencies. To implement cross-sector One Health activities, the analysis points towards establishing institutional One Health strategies and incorporating specific problem definitions when designing One Health projects to tackle coordination issues. Second, there are knowledge translation challenges among scientists and between scientists and policymakers. These challenges must be addressed by leaders, problem brokers, and policy entrepreneurs. Scientific knowledge must be translated across sectors and to policymakers to create heterophilous networks, use the knowledge

that exists within networks, and to provide opportunities for actors from the environment, social, and political science sectors to contribute to the knowledge pool. Third, there is a lack of understanding of the One Health approach. Efforts must be made to comprehend the One Health approach and what it means generally, for institutes and for specific projects. For this, schools should introduce the approach to consolidate the meaning and value that the approach holds for the public. Continuous capacity building for scientists must be performed to strengthen the use and operationalisation of the One Health approach.

As the use of the One Health approach is likely to become more widespread, it is imperative that the social sciences as well as further theoretical exploration must inform the design, implementation, and evaluation of the approach. For future research, studies involving bigger sample sizes can offer some additional insights and facilitate the attainment of statistically generalisable outputs. Further, selection of cases and survey studies should focus on engaging eastern European countries/participants. This could provide valuable insight into problem framing and agenda setting for the One Health approach tailored to the specific national context. Other country cases also could have provided interesting examples of One Health institutionalisation. Interesting would have been to investigate lower- and higher-income countries or countries with federal systems. There are many different angles and perspectives that One Health institutionalisation can be investigated through, which provides plenty of work for future research.

The One Health approach is a well-intended tool. To maintain these good intentions, scientists and policymakers must account for how to engage with the approach, implying sensitivity for local communities, practices, traditions, and beliefs. The One Health approach can then be regarded as more than a technical concept, but as a tool for scientific as well as policy enhancement and implementation. Scholars will need to take further initiative to explore the different perspectives of the approach. Politicians must integrate One Health notions into policies to enable the consolidation of the approach among the public and policymakers, appreciating the health and sustainable development of humans, animals, and the environment in our shared ecosystem.

7. *PhD project self-evaluation*

Methods:

Initially, an observation study was planned for 2020 that was supposed to be conducted at OHEJP stakeholder meetings. This methodological approach was abandoned due to COVID-19 lockdowns that hampered access to meetings.

The interview study was kept as part of the research design. Instead of doing them face-to-face, they were conducted both, online and face-to-face. This was due to travel restrictions. Conducting the interviews online did not compromise the content or the extent of discussions. The pandemic even opened up possibilities of adding questions about COVID-19 in relation to the One Health approach.

Fieldwork:

Two research stays were planned: a three-month stay in Sweden at the national veterinary institute and a three-month stay in Italy at the public health institute. The Swedish research stay was reduced to a one-week stay in autumn 2019, planned as an introductory meeting. While only a small fraction of the originally intended time, it nonetheless provided some useful contacts and insights into the

institute structures. However, the full three-month research stay in Sweden would likely have provided opportunities that might have led to different and possibly deeper impressions, collaborations, and a better understanding of the government agency itself. In Italy, a one-month research stay was accomplished at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità in autumn 2020. This period was productive in terms of conducting interviews and networking. However, strict COVID-19 regulations rendered it impossible to participate in ongoing meetings or other activities that might have provided in-depth insight into the institute processes and structures. One more month of fieldwork was conducted in Italy in autumn 2021, at which time I visited experts at regional veterinary institutes. While this deviated from the originally planned three-month research stay, the changes provided plenty of opportunity to network and conduct fieldwork. All in all, more interviews (both in Sweden and Italy) were conducted than initially planned, which demonstrates the flexibility of conducting online interviews.

Output:

In the original plan of the PhD project were scientific articles and a chapter planned as outputs. Some of the papers were (in some form) planned (Papers II, IV–VI). Papers I and III resulted from meetings with new colleagues and brainstorming on One Health issues, which led to the ideas for the manuscripts.*

*DOIs of Papers I – VI:

Paper I: The state of One Health research across disciplines and sectors – a bibliometric analysis.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146>

Paper II: One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>

Paper III: Assessing environmental factors within the One Health Approach.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>

Paper IV: Joint action against AMR with a One Health perspective. In *Steering against Superbugs: The Global Governance of Antimicrobial Resistance*. 10.1093/oso/9780192899477.003.0013

Paper V: Translating One Health knowledge across different institutional and political contexts in Europe. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42522-022-00074-x>

Paper VI: A governance and coordination perspective – Sweden’s and Italy’s approaches to implementing One Health. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100198>

8. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

This section is not filled out as my PhD project was initially not part of the OHEJP reporting procedures. Therefore, no deliverables and milestones were established.

Deliverables

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
					0	

9. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (global, EU, national or regional) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), national and international surveillance programmes.

Invited speaker at 11th One Health Sweden Scientific Meeting 2022: Pandemics and preparedness the 29-30 March. Presentation titled: 'Importance of connecting early and senior project collaborators under the One Health umbrella'.

JRP NOVA 'Surveillance barriers and opportunities as perceived by veterinary practitioners': I was involved in conducting an exploratory study on barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health approach within four EU countries. I carried out online semi-structured interviews of veterinary practitioners (from Sweden and Norway) and analysed the interviews. This was led by Maria-Eleni Filippitzi.

The purpose of conducting the interviews was to identify the perceptions of OHEJP participants about critical barriers reducing the cost effectiveness of foodborne zoonoses surveillance (e.g. technical, legal, ethical, financial, socio-political, educational, data communication barriers). Perceptions regarding opportunities to improve the cost effectiveness of surveillance were also assessed. The outcome aimed to enable a comprehensive approach to surveillance optimisation.

The questionnaire covered two parts:

- Part A – Questions related to you as a respondent (age, area of expertise, et cetera).
- Part B – Open free-text questions about barriers and opportunities for surveillance.

An outcome of this analysis will be a scientific article, led by Maria-Eleni Filippitzi.

10. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders

None

11. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

Being part of a large, EU-funded Horizon 2020 project provided invaluable access to stakeholders from different countries, sectors, and disciplines. Further, the OHEJP provided contacts for the interview as well as survey study and shared the survey invitations through their internal email lists. The Horizon 2020 project offered many opportunities for courses and networking, but also entailed an extensive amount of reporting. While extensive and time-consuming, these reporting procedures were a valuable contribution for the PhD project, as they taught among other things techniques to disseminate research findings. This was done continuously through conferences and engagement via social networking sites (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter).

Further, the Annual Scientific Meetings provided opportunity to disseminate findings and learn about other ongoing research. Especially the in-person conferences led to fruitful discussions and provided opportunity to engage in conference organisation, where I facilitated a One Health quiz (OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting, 2021).

12. *Transferrable skills and Training*

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Workshop 1 & 2 Write an article for publication	Journal and editors; Structures of articles; how to write a good article	26.10.2021	Roskilde University
Quantitative research methods workshop	Sectional simple and multivariate regressions	16.09.2021	Roskilde University
Workshop on Research Communication	Use the journalistic toolbox; Find the good story in your research; Write to get read: Dissemination strategies	09.09.2021	Roskilde University
One Health EJP Summer School 2021 Global One Health - Environmental Issues in One Health (2 weeks)	From risk assessment to surveillance	06.08.2021	OHEJP
One Health European Joint Programme Cogwheel Workshop	Finding synergies and opportunities for knowledge transfer and/or collaboration.	25.11.2020	OHEJP
Research data management and the FAIR principles in Open Science	Storage of data; Metadata; data management plan; FAIR principles	05.11.2020	Roskilde University
One Health EJP Summer School 2020 Global One Health (2 weeks)	From Research to Practice	28.08.2020	OHEJP
Qualitative Research Interviews	Qualitative Research Interviews	12.06.2020	Roskilde University
Qualitative Research Methods	Interviews, observation, document analysis; surveys, cases, focus groups	29.05.2020	Roskilde University

Research Design Course	Research design development, research questions	13.05.2020	Roskilde University
NVivo Beginners & Advanced	NVivo theory and practical training	7. & 10.01.2020	Roskilde University
Systematic literature search	Systematic literature search and analysis approaches	09.11.2019	Roskilde University
Research Ethics and Integrity	Ethics and Integrity	04.11.2019	Roskilde University

13. Ethical Reviews

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020

The responses to previous ethical reviewers comments have been accepted and this is closed.

14. Scientific Publications

Publication date	Publication title	Authors	DOI reference	Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? *please specify embargo length	Is it a Gold Open Access?
December 2020	The state of One Health research across disciplines and sectors – a bibliometric analysis	Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden, Olivier Rubin, Snorre Sylvester Frid-Nielsen	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146	https://zenodo.org/record/4304170#.ZEZAlnZBxPY	Yes		Yes
13.01.2021	Attention to the Tripartite's one health measures in national action plans on antimicrobial resistance	Louise Munkholm, Olivier Rubin, Erik Bækkeskov, Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden	https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-021-00277-y	https://zenodo.org/record/7634461#.ZEZCm3ZBxPY	No	Yes, 12 months	
30.06.2021	One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination	Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden	https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483	https://zenodo.org/record/5045277#.ZEZCOHZBxPY	Yes		Yes

05.03.2021	Assessing environmental factors within the One Health Approach	Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden, Alberto Mantovani	https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240	https://zenodo.org/record/4590352#.ZEZCZXZBxPY	Yes		Yes
31.01.2023	Translating One Health knowledge across different institutional and political contexts in Europe	Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden	https://doi.org/10.1186/s42522-022-00074-x	https://zenodo.org/record/7610384#.ZEZCcnZBxPY	Yes		Yes
December 2022	A governance and coordination perspective – Sweden’s and Italy’s approaches to implementing One Health	Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100198	https://zenodo.org/record/7360313#.ZEZCfXZBxPY	Yes		Yes

15. Additional Outputs

/

16. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

I produced five scientific articles and one chapter throughout my PhD project:

Paper I: The state of One Health research across disciplines and sectors – a bibliometric analysis. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146>

Paper II: One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>

Paper III: Assessing environmental factors within the One Health Approach. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>

Paper IV: Joint action against AMR with a One Health perspective. In Steering against Superbugs: The Global Governance of Antimicrobial Resistance. 10.1093/oso/9780192899477.003.0013

Paper V: Translating One Health knowledge across different institutional and political contexts in Europe. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42522-022-00074-x>

Paper VI: A governance and coordination perspective – Sweden's and Italy's approaches to implementing One Health. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100198>

Paper III draws attention to the environment component of the One Health approach and provides examples of its importance and engagement opportunities. It relies on two cases: Antimicrobial resistance in relation to the Danish approach to surveillance (DANMAP); and mycotoxins in relation to Italian farming practices.

Papers VI and II provide specific examples about One Health institutionalisation in Sweden and Italy. They highlight practical challenges and opportunities that can be used to strengthen the One Health approach within institutions to foster collaboration and communication.

Paper V highlights the lack of considering contexts and the lack of a common language among scientists and policymakers. This revealed how One Health often remained an abstract concept, which called for establishing a clear meaning of the One Health approach in relation to the context in which it is being implemented; for example, by way of engaging social and political scientists, who can provide their expertise to comprehend societal and political contexts. The study provides insight into political processes in terms of political attention and agenda setting, and it contributes to an understanding of the leadership characteristics needed for the One Health approach.

17. One Health impact

The PhD project has a unique angle on One Health. It investigates the implementation and institutionalisation of the One Health approach within public health, veterinary, food, and environment institutes. The results of this research can be used by regional or national authorities and

stakeholders of the OHEJP to evaluate and consider their coordination and collaboration efforts. It produces useful knowledge and examples for institutes on challenges for collaboration and how to overcome those. It provides practical guidance on who to engage with and how, e.g. via establishing institutional One Health strategies. For international stakeholders, it can provide useful information about improvements of existing /planned surveillance programmes. This includes discussions about existing surveillance activities and specific aspects that must be improved, especially for antimicrobial resistance surveillance. Further contributions are discussions about strengthening cross-sector collaboration in terms of communication and harmonising data to prevent duplication as well as strengthen efficacy of disease surveillance programmes and collaborations. The impact for the stakeholders of the OHEJP also include practical examples about possible applications of social and environmental scientists and a call to engage eastern European countries in One Health-related activities.

On a political level, it will provide insight into sharing and translating knowledge between scientists and politicians. The PhD project reveals opportunities to support One Health-related policymaking through considering knowledge translation and societal challenges. It proposes ways to maintain cooperative structures (e.g., with policy entrepreneurs and problem brokers, honing leadership skills and strengthening heterophil networks).

The OEHJP has supported PhD project not only with facilitating contacts, but especially with its exceptional network. This has led to partner with the Swedish National Veterinary Institute and the Italian National Institute of Health. The collaborations included research and fieldwork stays at the institutes, where I conducted formal and informal interviews with experts and got to know the structures and procedures of the institutes. Additionally, it resulted in a co-authored scientific article (with Alberto Mantovani) in relation to environmental considerations within the One Health approach via the two cases of antimicrobial resistance and mycotoxins. Through the research stay at the Swedish National Veterinary Institute, I was introduced to the NOVA project. I engaged in the project through supporting the development of the interview guide, interviewing Swedish and Norwegian experts and analysing the qualitative data. This has provided invaluable experiences that went beyond the topic of the PhD project and helped to better understand the One Health approach and all its components and actors.

18. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>One Health Sweden Scientific Meeting</i>		
Date:	<i>29.-30.03.2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Uppsala, Sweden</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>YES</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>

<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	70	<i>Media</i>	10
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – 3MT		
Date:	11.04.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – Poster presentation		
Date:	11.-13.04.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – Roundtable discussion		
Date:	13.04.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No

Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	20
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	ONE – Health, Environment, Society		
Date:	21.-23.06.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	20
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	Roskilde Conference- GRASP		
Date:	18-20.11.2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			

	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	50	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	14th European Public Health Conference		
Date:	10-12 November 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	YES
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	Yes	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	20
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – 3MT		
Date:	10.06.2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	20
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – Oral Presentation		
Date:	10.06.2021		
Place:	Copenhagen, Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No

<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – Organising team for kahoot quizzes		
Date:	09.-11.06.2021		
Place:	Copenhagen, Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	Yes	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	No
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	6th cogwheel workshop between SafeConsume and OHEJP		
Date:	25.11.2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	YES
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	YES
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	WOHC - 6th World One Health Congress		
Date:	14. - 18.06.2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No

<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	Yes	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP - ASM		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	Yes	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

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